

Analytical decoupling of focus position and magnification in a three-lens system with a Galilean core

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Abstract. A three-lens optical system is presented that enables independent adjustment of focus position and magnification using two degrees of freedom. The system is based on paraxial ray matrix formalism and extends the functionality of a Galilean telescope by allowing the focus position to be decoupled from the magnification. In a special case, one degree of freedom is frozen, and the system exhibits a constant magnification equal to that of the Galilean telescope while enabling a variable focus position. To the best of the author's knowledge, this operating point has not yet been described in the literature. Conditions for achieving such properties are derived analytically and compared to the behavior of the general and classical Galilean telescope, which feature one and zero degrees of freedom, respectively. The theoretical predictions are supported by numerical simulations. The analytical approach demonstrated with the three-lens system may be used as a guide for optics design as it potentially allows for further optical properties decoupling by adding more degrees of freedom.

Keywords: three-lens system, degrees of freedom, Galilean telescope, analytical optics design, reverse-mapping optimization, ray transfer matrix

1 Introduction

The development of versatile optical systems with tunable properties is a key objective in modern optical engineering. Compact setups that enable independent control over focus position and magnification are of interest for applications in laser beam shaping and compact imaging systems. Those systems are mostly designed by using single-lens equivalent focal lengths and iterative skew raytracing methods¹⁻³ with lenses added/adapted to match the desired properties. Matrix-based optical methods were introduced by T. Smith in 1930 (see E. Hecht³ p. 260) and brought to closer attention by K. Halbach⁴ in 1960, who systematically derived matrices for propagation and refraction. Since then, matrix-based methods have been proven as a powerful optical design tool, offering a compact analytic framework for modeling optical systems^{5,6}.

33 Beyond its value in first order raytracing, this formalism has been applied in fields like intraocular
34 lens calculation⁷ and schematic eye modeling⁸. The approach in the present research, similarly,
35 derives global system equations analytically from the ray matrices, but then follows a distinct
36 mathematical path that focuses on the degrees of freedom of a given optical system, namely
37 independent setting of magnification and focus position.

38 To begin with a very simple, long-known configuration that provides constant magnification at
39 infinite focus, the classical Galilean telescope⁹ is employed, which consists of a diverging and a
40 converging lens. In this classical implementation, the distance between the two lenses is fixed to
41 the sum of their focal lengths, resulting in zero optical degrees of freedom. In its generalized form,
42 the Galilean telescope allows a variable distance between the lenses, introducing one degree of
43 freedom. However, this inherently links magnification and focus position, making independent
44 control impossible. This limitation restricts its use in applications where decoupled control of
45 optical parameters is required.

46 To overcome this limitation, a three-lens optical system is introduced that extends the Galilean
47 telescope by incorporating a third lens and two independently adjustable propagation distances l_1
48 and l_2 . By using the analytical matrix-based approach, these two mechanical degrees of freedom
49 translate to two optical degrees of freedom, therefore enabling independent tuning of both focus
50 position and magnification. The analytical findings are visualized by numerical simulations and
51 selected application scenarios for the three-lens system are outlined.

52

53 **2 Analytical method for the three-lens system**

54 *2.1 Matrix formalism for a parallel laser input*

55 We consider a paraxial optical system composed of three thin lenses L_1 , L_2 and L_3 with focal
56 lengths $f_1 < 0$, $f_2 > 0$ and $f_3 > 0$, and two propagation distances l_1 and l_2 between the lenses.
57 Fig. 1 shows a schematic of the system along with a laser beam with size Δy_{in} and negligible
58 divergence, $\alpha_{in,l} \approx 0$, entering the system via L_1 . This lens is placed at $z = 0$, followed by a
59 propagation over a variable distance l_1 to lens L_2 , then over a variable distance l_2 to lens L_3 , and
60 finally over the variable distance l_3 to the focus plane. To realize two mechanical degrees of
61 freedom, distances l_1 and l_2 must be independently adjustable. Typically, this can be accomplished

62 by a stacked setup (not shown in Fig. 1): L_1 is mounted on a compact translation stage that rides
 63 atop a common stage carrying both L_1 and L_2 . Moving the common stage changes only l_2 , while
 64 the inner stage permits variation only of l_1 . Lens L_3 remains fixed throughout.

65
 66 **Fig. 1** Schematic of the three-lens system and a laser beam allowing independent tuning of focus position and
 67 magnification. Lenses L_1 , L_2 and L_3 are separated by independently adjustable distances l_1 and l_2 . Variables f_i
 68 denote focal lengths, l_3 is the propagation distance after L_3 , Δy_{in} and Δy_{out} are input and output laser beam
 69 diameters, $\alpha_{in,l}$ and $\alpha_{out,l}$ denote the input and output divergence of the laser beam, respectively.

70 The system is described using $ABCD$ matrix formalism, where each optical element and free space
 71 section contributes a corresponding ray transfer matrix⁶. The total system matrix M_{sys} is:

$$72 \quad M_{sys} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & l_3 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -f_3^{-1} & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & l_2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -f_2^{-1} & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & l_1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -f_1^{-1} & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

73 With a collimated input beam, the optical behavior of the system can be captured by the upper left
 74 matrix element A of the system matrix. Two important conditions can be derived from the matrix
 75 element A . First, the focusing condition for the system corresponds to the beam being focused on
 76 a certain distance f_{sys} behind lens L_3 , independent of its initial size Δy_{in} . For a given set of lens
 77 parameters f_i , this is expressed as:

$$78 \quad A(l_1, l_2, l_3 = f_{sys}) = 0. \quad (2)$$

79 Second, the magnification condition corresponds to the magnification $M = \Delta y_{out} / \Delta y_{in}$ of the
 80 input beam diameter, before the final propagation, and is given by:

$$81 \quad A(l_1, l_2, l_3 = 0) = M. \quad (3)$$

82 These two expressions with four unknowns link the independently tunable mechanical variables
 83 l_1 and l_2 to independent optical output beam parameters f_{sys} and M , thus defining two optical
 84 degrees of freedom. This mapping from (l_1, l_2) to (f_{sys}, M) is the key functional capability of the
 85 lens system described here.

86 2.2 General case of the three-lens system

87 In the general case, the system focus position is given by solving Eq. (2) for f_{sys} . This gives:

88
$$f_{\text{sys}} = \frac{M f_1 f_2 f_3}{l_1 l_2 - l_1 f_2 - l_1 f_3 - l_2 f_1 - l_2 f_2 + f_1 f_2 + f_1 f_3 + f_2 f_3}. \quad (4)$$

89 The sensitivity of the adjustment of f_{sys} with respect to a change in l_1 and l_2 by Δl_1 or Δl_2 ,
90 respectively, can be calculated using the Gaussian error propagation formula:

91
$$\Delta f_{\text{sys}} = \frac{f_{\text{sys}}^2}{f_2^2 f_1^2 M^2} (f_2^2 \Delta l_1 + (l_1 - f_2 - f_1)^2 \Delta l_2). \quad (5)$$

92 Note the quadratic dependence on focus position and magnification of Δf_{sys} with respect to errors
93 in setting both l_1 and l_2 . Δl_1 is additionally scaled by f_1^{-2} , whereas Δl_2 has scalars predominantly
94 by position l_1^2 , and by f_2^{-2} and f_1^{-2} .

95 The magnification M at L_3 , given explicitly by Eq. (3), can be arranged as:

96
$$M = \left(1 - \frac{l_2}{f_2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{l_1}{|f_1|}\right) + \frac{l_2}{|f_1|}. \quad (6)$$

97 Note that the magnification is independent of the focal length f_3 . The sensitivity of the setting of
98 M can be given once again by using the maximum error formula:

99
$$\Delta M = \frac{1}{|f_1| f_2} (|l_2 - f_2| \Delta l_1 + |l_1 - f_2 - f_1| \Delta l_2). \quad (7)$$

100 For a given set of lens parameters f_i , we find $f_{\text{sys}}(l_1, l_2)$ and $M(l_1, l_2)$, with the two mechanical
101 degrees of freedom l_1 and l_2 and the two optical degrees of freedom f_{sys} and M . Therefore,
102 independent adjustment of the distances should allow for independent adjustment of focus position
103 and beam size.

104 To ensure a well-defined working range, that is positive values for l_1 and l_2 , the denominator in
105 Eq. (4) must not vanish. The condition for this divergence (i.e. $f_{\text{sys}} \rightarrow \infty$) defines a critical
106 parameter regime. Upon solving the pole in Eq. (4) for $l_1 > 0$ and $l_2 > 0$, and using $f_1 < 0$ and
107 $f_2 > 0$, the following boundary condition for the lens' focal lengths is obtained:

108
$$f_3 > \frac{f_2 |f_1|}{f_2 - |f_1|} = \frac{f_2^2}{f_2 - |f_1|} - f_2. \quad (8)$$

109 Since L_3 needs to be a convex lens $f_3 > 0$, Eq. (8) directly shows that:

110
$$f_2 > |f_1|. \quad (9)$$

111 Equations (8) and (9) are the optical design boundary conditions and ensure that collimated output
112 beams and large values of f_{sys} can be accommodated within the functionality of the three-lens
113 system. However, even if the values for f_2 and f_3 are chosen such, that the singularity of $f_{\text{sys}}(l_1, l_2)$

114 lies slightly below $l_1 = 0$ or $l_2 = 0$, a finite and practically useful work range for small f_{sys} values
 115 remains accessible. Due to the low steepness of the $f_{\text{sys}}(l_1, l_2)$ curve in this regime, a very precise
 116 adjustment of f_{sys} is possible at small values of l_1 and l_2 .

117 2.3 Special case of the three-lens system

118 A key feature of the proposed system is its ability to maintain a constant magnification of $f_2/|f_1|$
 119 while continuously varying the focal position with only one degree of freedom. To explore the
 120 condition under which this decoupling becomes possible, we reconsider the magnification
 121 condition Eq. (3) along with Eq. (6), and impose a magnification of $f_2/|f_1|$:

$$122 \quad M = \left(1 - \frac{l_2}{f_2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{l_1}{|f_1|}\right) + \frac{l_2}{|f_1|} \stackrel{?}{=} \frac{f_2}{|f_1|}. \quad (10)$$

123 Solving Eq. (10) for l_2 , we find that l_1 and f_1 vanish:

$$124 \quad l_2 = \frac{f_2(f_2 - |f_1| - l_1)}{f_2 - |f_1| - l_1} = f_2. \quad (11)$$

125 Thus, the condition $l_2 = f_2$ ensures that the magnification is fixed at $f_2/|f_1|$, independent of
 126 distance l_1 . Substituting $l_2 = f_2$ into Eqns. (4) and (6), in turn, gives the focal position only in
 127 dependence of distance l_1 :

$$128 \quad f_{\text{sys}} = \frac{f_2^2}{l_1 - f_2 - f_1 + \frac{f_2^2}{f_3}}. \quad (12)$$

129 The special case of the three-lens system has only one mechanical degree of freedom which is l_1 .
 130 However, since the other degree of freedom is frozen at a condition, where l_1 has no influence on
 131 magnification at L_3 , tuning of the focal position at constant beam size is accessible.

132 The sensitivity of the tuning with respect to l_1 can again be given by the Gaussian error formula:

$$133 \quad \Delta f_{\text{sys}} = \frac{f_{\text{sys}}^2}{f_2^2} \Delta l_1. \quad (13)$$

134 Equation (13) reveals that the sensitivity of setting f_{sys} , depends quadratically on the target focus
 135 position itself. Specifically, for small values of f_{sys} , large changes in l_1 result in only minor
 136 adjustments of the focus position. Conversely, for large values of f_{sys} , even small variations in l_1
 137 cause substantial shifts in the focal plane. Notably, when $f_{\text{sys}} = f_2$, the sensitivity of the focal shift
 138 is equal to that of a single lens configuration. Thus, the focal length of lens L_2 effectively marks
 139 the pivot point: above this value, the system responds increasingly to changes in l_1 , whereas below
 140 it, the response decreases. It is noted that Eqns. (12) and (13) imply a setting of l_2 with ideal

141 precision. If the error Δl_2 is considered, Eq. (5) can be used along with $l_2 = f_2$, to derive the error
 142 formula for the special case:

$$143 \quad \Delta f_{\text{sys}} = \frac{f_{\text{sys}}^2}{f_2^2} \Delta l_1 + \frac{f_{\text{sys}}^2}{f_2^4} (l_1 - f_2 - f_1)^2 \Delta l_2. \quad (14)$$

144 Upon examining the pole of Eq. (12), we find that afocal behavior and large values of f_{sys} become
 145 accessible with positive l_1 values, if the following boundary condition is fulfilled:

$$146 \quad f_3 > \frac{f_2^2}{f_2 - |f_1|}. \quad (15)$$

147 This condition is stricter than the general condition given by Eq. (8), i.e. the focal length of L_3
 148 needs to be increased by the value of f_2 . Like in the general case, an additional work range with
 149 small f_{sys} values arises for other combinations of f_1 due to poles with negative l_1 values.

150 2.4 Comparison with the Galilean telescope

151 2.4.1 Matrix formalism and degrees of freedom

152 The general Galilean telescope with one degree of freedom can be derived with the same matrix
 153 formalism as shown above, if $f_3 \rightarrow \infty$. In the case of thin lenses, the matrix for L_3 then approaches
 154 the unity matrix, effectively removing L_3 from the setup. The matrices for l_2 and l_3 may be
 155 combined into a common matrix for the final propagation. The focusing condition for the general
 156 Galilean telescope is then given by:

$$157 \quad A(l_1, l_2 + l_3 = f_{\text{sys}}^{\text{Gal}}) = 0. \quad (16)$$

158 Solving Eq. (16) for the focus position yields:

$$159 \quad f_{\text{sys}}^{\text{Gal}} = \frac{f_2 |f_1| M^{\text{Gal}}}{l_1 - f_2 - f_1}. \quad (17)$$

160 Note that Eq. (17) may also be derived by plugging $l_2 = 0$ and $f_3 \rightarrow \infty$ into Eq. (4). Accordingly,
 161 M^{Gal} can be derived from Eqns. (3) and (6):

$$162 \quad A(l_1, l_2 = 0, l_3 = 0) = M^{\text{Gal}} = 1 + \frac{l_1}{|f_1|}. \quad (18)$$

163 Since $f_{\text{sys}}^{\text{Gal}}$ and M^{Gal} both only depend on l_1 , only one mechanical degree of freedom is present in
 164 the general Galilean telescope. Therefore, independent adjustment of focal position and
 165 magnification is prohibited.

166 However, if we now ask for the magnification at a distance l_2 after the second lens, just at that
 167 point where L_3 had been removed, we find that the magnification of the three-lens system and the
 168 general Galilean telescope are the same and given by Eq. (6). Therefore, upon imposing $f_2/|f_1|$,

169 which gives the special case of the three-lens system as shown by Eq. (11), the same condition,
 170 $l_2 = f_2$ is derived for the general Galilean telescope. This means that the magnification of the
 171 general Galilean telescope at distance $l_2 = f_2$ behind the second lens is always given by $f_2/|f_1|$,
 172 independent of the setting of l_1 . Therefore, the frozen degree of freedom from the special case of
 173 the three-lens system is also inherent in the general Galilean telescope, but it cannot be leveraged
 174 as such. By placing a transparent object, i.e. a cuvette with water, at distance $l_2 = f_2$ behind the
 175 second lens, the magnification at the entrance of said object would also stay constant, while the
 176 focal position is varied inside the object with l_1 . It might also be used as a reference point in laser
 177 materials processing. However, the hidden degree of freedom is inaccessible for imaging purposes,
 178 since the light from an object is only captured by L_2 . By placing a third lens at $l_2 = f_2$, this hidden
 179 degree of freedom becomes accessible also for imaging purposes (see Sec. 2.5), since L_3 now
 180 captures the constant beam diameter at this position. Therefore, in contrast to the general Galilean
 181 telescope, the special case of the three-lens system enables a focus scan of different objects located
 182 along the z-axis, while keeping the magnification constant.

183 The special case of the Galilean telescope has zero degrees of freedom. This is the classical and
 184 most abundant use of the device, i.e. as a laser beam expander. As Eq. (17) shows, the general
 185 Galilean telescope has a pole at $l_1 = f_2 - |f_1|$. At this point the special case of the Galilean
 186 telescope is attained with a fixed l_1 value and a collimated beam with a magnification of $f_2/|f_1|$.
 187 The special case of the three-lens system on the other hand gives a collimated beam with constant
 188 magnification of $f_2/|f_1|$ at $l_2 = f_2$ and $l_1 = f_2 - |f_1| - f_2^2/f_3$. With the general three-lens system
 189 however, due to the two degrees of freedom, a different l_2 value changes magnification at L_3 ,
 190 while the pole for l_1 is adapted accordingly, therefore allowing different magnifications of
 191 collimated beams (see Sec. 2.4.2).

192 2.4.2 Linear relationship with the three-lens system

193 To increase analytical insight into the relationship between the three-lens system and its Galilean
 194 core, we can now express Eqns. (4) and (6) in terms of Eqns. (17) and (18). For the magnification
 195 we find:

$$196 \quad M = \left(1 - \frac{l_2}{f_2}\right) M^{\text{Gal}} + \frac{l_2}{|f_1|}. \quad (19)$$

197 This resembles a linear equation with a variable slope. Therefore, any given $M^{\text{Gal}}(l_1)$, is modulated
 198 by the three-lens system to give a plurality of M . The vertical offset ensures the special case $l_2 =$

199 f_2 and allows l_2 to be slightly higher than f_2 , whereas $|f_1|$ scales the offset and defines how much
 200 l_1 needs to be increased to increase M^{Gal} . For example, at $f_{\text{sys}} < f_2$, M^{Gal} approaches infinity and
 201 the maximum accessible magnification M_{max} is only limited by the form factor of the three-lens
 202 system, more specifically the limited inter-lens distances. M_{min} then can easily be approached by
 203 increasing l_2 , since the slope in Eq. (19) cannot be greater than one. However, at $f_{\text{sys}} = f_3$,
 204 meaning $l_1 = f_2 - |f_1|$, all lines cross, independent of their slope, resulting in a single accessible
 205 magnification. At this point we find $M = M^{\text{Gal}} = f_2/|f_1|$ and the functionality of the three-lens
 206 system collapses into that of the classical Galilean telescope plus a third lens. At larger values of
 207 f_{sys} , l_1 gets smaller, thereby enabling $M^{\text{Gal}} < f_2/|f_1|$. Now the intercept $l_2/|f_1|$ has more control
 208 on magnification.

209 To express the relationship for f_{sys} , we use the single lens equivalent focal length, Eq. (4) divided
 210 by M , and express it in terms of the equivalent focal length of the Galilean telescope, which is Eq.
 211 (17) divided by M^{Gal} . We get:

$$212 \quad \frac{f_{\text{sys}}}{M} = \frac{f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}} f_3}{f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}} + f_3 - l_2}. \quad (20)$$

213 Since the equations for matrix focus position and single lens equivalent focal length share the same
 214 pole, Eq. (20) can be interpreted as a generator for new poles: $f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}}$ has a pole at $l_1 = f_2 - |f_1|$,
 215 however, with the three-lens system, every l_1 from $f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}} \neq \infty$, can be converted to a pole in post,
 216 by a proper choice of l_2 , that is $l_2 = f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}} + f_3$, with f_3 as a horizontal offset. This gives rise to a
 217 continuous line of poles in the (l_1, l_2) plane, effectively extending the single Galilean pole to a
 218 tunable family, controlled by f_3 . The pole line defines all combinations (l_1, l_2) that preserve
 219 collimation and thereby enables the system to generate a continuum of magnifications for
 220 collimated beams. At $f_{\text{sys}} = f_3$, $f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}}$ is infinity, consequently for $f_{\text{sys}} < f_3$, $f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}}$ is positive and
 221 heads towards zero if l_1 is increased. In turn, for $f_{\text{sys}} > f_3$, $f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}}$ is negative. Therefore, in this
 222 region, we find $l_2 > f_{\text{sl}}^{\text{Gal}} + f_3$.

223 An overall linear relationship can be derived, when the inverse of Eq. (20) is used along with $f_{\text{sys}}^{\text{Gal}}$
 224 and M^{Gal} :

$$225 \quad \frac{M}{f_{\text{sys}}} = \frac{1}{f_3} + \frac{M^{\text{Gal}}}{f_{\text{sys}}^{\text{Gal}}} \left(1 - \frac{l_2}{f_3}\right). \quad (21)$$

226 This result compares both systems quotients and reveals that the three-lens system acts as a
 227 linear transformer of the Galilean beam quotient, with tunable slope and offset controlled by l_2

228 and f_3 : Any given combination $(M^{\text{Gal}}, f_{\text{sys}}^{\text{Gal}})$ is converted to a multitude of combinations
 229 (M, f_{sys}) by the additional propagation and lens L_3 .

230 *2.5 Reverse operation and image formation*

231 In paraxial optics, every system matrix is symplectic, meaning it preserves the phase space area
 232 spanned by the ray height y and angle α relative to the z -axis. This area does not change during
 233 beam propagation. As a direct consequence, the paraxial imaging behavior of the system is
 234 invariant under optical reversal. In this scenario, the light in Fig. 1 now emerges from f_{sys} and
 235 travels in the negative direction of the z -axis, with its diverging angle being equal to $\alpha_{\text{out},l}$.
 236 Consequently, a light bundle emerging from $y_{\text{object}} = 0$ and leaving the three-lens system via
 237 ocular lens L_1 has a diverging angle of $\alpha_{\text{in},l} = 0$ (parallel mode). In this mode, each object point
 238 located at a fixed axial distance $z = f_{\text{sys}}$, but at a different transverse position $y_{\text{object}} \neq 0$, is
 239 mapped to a parallel bundle of rays with characteristic tilt angle $\alpha_{\text{in},l} \neq 0$ with respect to the z -
 240 axis. The original distance of the object points from the z -axis depends on the tilt angle by:

$$241 \quad y_{\text{object}} = f_{\text{sys}} \alpha_{\text{in},l}. \quad (22)$$

242 In the forward laser picture, this corresponds to a laser illuminating the system with tilt angle
 243 $\alpha_{\text{in},l} \neq 0$ (see also Gerrard and Burch⁶ p. 41). Equation (22) directly translates to a definition for
 244 angular magnification of the object as defined by the laser picture:

$$245 \quad M = \frac{\alpha_{\text{in},l}}{\alpha_{\text{out},l}} = \frac{\Delta y_{\text{out}}}{\Delta y_{\text{in}}}. \quad (23)$$

246 In the case of a thin object being mapped to parallel bundles with different $\alpha_{\text{in},l}$, this angular spread
 247 determines how large the object appears when viewed through the system via the ocular lens L_1 .
 248 Because this magnification can be continuously tuned via the lens separations using l_1 and l_2 , the
 249 three-lens system enables zoom functionality over a wide range of distances.

250 Since the single lens equivalent focal length of the system is the same in both directions, a second
 251 distinct imaging mode arises (direct imaging mode). In direct imaging mode, a real image is
 252 formed at a finite distance from the ocular lens L_1 , i.e. on a screen. This corresponds to the classical
 253 concept of image formation by convergence of rays. Therefore, the three-lens system behaves like
 254 an objective, projecting an image onto a detector, albeit independent control over object position,
 255 magnification and image position—the latter being given by a multitude of $\alpha_{\text{in},l}$ —is lost, as one
 256 degree of freedom is missing.

257 **3 Numerical results for the three-lens system**

258 *3.1 Accessible magnifications at different focus positions*

259 In this approach, fixed focal lengths for the lenses were chosen to be $f_1 = -5$ cm, $f_2 = 20$ cm
 260 and $f_3 = 50$ cm, and substituted into Eqns. (4) and (6). The resulting system of two equations has
 261 four unknowns f_{sys} , M , l_1 and l_2 . Values for f_{sys} in the range 1 to 600 cm in varying increments
 262 and M in the range of 0.1 to 12.0 in 0.1 increments were systematically substituted into the system
 263 of equations and tested for solutions with $0.5 \text{ cm} < l_1, l_2 < 50 \text{ cm}$, the form factor of the system.
 264 The focal length f_3 was subsequently changed to 40 cm, 30 cm and 20 cm, with the procedure
 265 repeated each time. The numerical simulation was also conducted on the general Galilean
 266 telescope with the same value for f_{sys} , and M^{Gal} being the magnification at L_2 . Results are shown
 267 in graphs (a) to (d) on Fig. 2.

268 **Fig. 2** Accessible magnification range (gray area) with envelope M_{max} and M_{min} (black solid lines) for each focus
 269 position. $f_1 = -5$ cm, $f_2 = 20$ cm and $f_3 = 50$ cm (a), 40 cm (b), 30 cm (c), 20 cm (d). The magnification of the
 270 general Galilean telescope M^{Gal} is shown for comparison (black dashed line).
 271 For $f_3 = 50$ cm (a), the magnification range, denoted by M_{max} and M_{min} , at large f_{sys} is
 272 approximately 3 – 8, with a broad maximum accessible range around $f_{\text{sys}} \approx 400$ cm. Upon
 273

274 approaching $f_{\text{sys}} = f_3$ the magnification range strongly declines to result in a single accessible
 275 magnification $f_2/|f_1|$. Subsequently the magnification range increases again, with a maximum
 276 range of 1 – 10 around $f_{\text{sys}} \approx f_2$. For $f_{\text{sys}} < f_2$ the accessible magnification range then declines
 277 again. The magnification of the Galilean telescope for large f_{sys} approaches $f_2/|f_1|$ and is always
 278 well contained within the three-lens system. For $f_{\text{sys}} < f_3$, the magnification is tunable below M^{Gal}
 279 as shown in section 2.4.2. If f_3 is chosen to be 40 cm (b), the accessible magnification range for
 280 large f_{sys} declines to around 3 – 6, with the maximum now being sharper and shifted to $f_{\text{sys}} \approx$
 281 125 cm, where the range of M persists to be around 3 – 8. For smaller values of f_{sys} , the behavior
 282 is basically the same as described above, with the exception that the near field magnification range
 283 is distributed slightly narrower around f_2 and slightly shifted towards zero. If $f_3 = 30$ cm (c) is
 284 chosen, the accessible magnification range for large f_{sys} is around 2.5 – 4.5. The maximum
 285 accessible range is again sharper and shifted to $f_{\text{sys}} \approx 70$ cm, where it is maintained at 3 – 8. In
 286 the case of $f_3 = f_2$ (d), the special case of the three-lens system is no longer included for large
 287 values of f_{sys} , as the three-lens design rule from Eq. (15), would demand f_3 to be at least 27 cm.
 288 It is noted that the term “form factor” takes on a literal meaning in Fig. 2 as limitations of l_1 and
 289 l_2 significantly alter the shape of M_{max} compared to the shape described in Sec. 2.4.2. More
 290 precisely, the near field maximum magnification range is shifted from zero towards f_2 and the
 291 second maximum magnification range is shifted from f_3^+ to infinity, both accompanied by a
 292 broadening of the range. As can be seen in Fig. 2, the extent of these shifts depends on the specific
 293 lens combination.

294 3.2 Tuning range and precision of tuning

295 To assess the sensitivity of the three-lens system with respect to a change in l_1 and l_2 in absolute
 296 and relative position, we use Eqns. (5) and (7). Fig. 3 illustrates this sensitivity using heatmaps
 297 along with isolines f_{sys} and M for three different lens configurations, assuming $\Delta l_1 = \Delta l_2 = 1$ cm.
 298 Plots (a) to (c) show the variation of f_{sys} for lens combinations with $f_1 = 5$ cm, $f_2 = 20$ cm and
 299 $f_3 = 50, 30$ and 20 cm, respectively. Plot (d) shows the variation of magnification, independent
 300 of f_3 . In (d), two isolines, one from the special case $l_2 = f_2$ and one from functionality collapse
 301 $l_1 = f_2 - |f_1|$, divide the heatmap into four quadrants. Herein, M is tuned around both isolines
 302 with copies inverted through the centre and increased steepness of the tuning, giving the heatmap

303 and the isolines the resemblance of an asymmetric saddle. Comparing plots (a) to (c), it is evident,
 304 that the choice of L_3 determines whether magnifications for a given f_{sys} are set by using the upper
 305 two quadrants ($f_{\text{sys}} < f_3$) or the lower two quadrants ($f_{\text{sys}} > f_3$). L_3 also alters the onset of the
 306 pole curve (see Sec. 2.4.2). For example, in plot (a) all $f_{\text{sys}} > f_3$ reach into the lower right quadrant
 307 of (d) thereby enabling several magnifications at large values of f_{sys} , whereas in plot (c), only low
 308 values of f_{sys} , slightly higher than f_3 , can access this quadrant.

309
 310 **Fig. 3** Precision of tunability Δf_{sys} with $f_3 = 50$ cm (a), 30 cm (b) and 20 cm (c), and ΔM (d). All graphs have
 311 $f_1 = 5$ cm and $f_2 = 20$ cm. Isolines for f_{sys} and M are shown as white solid lines. Areas with $f_{\text{sys}} < 0$ or $M < 0$
 312 are shown as white surface.

313 4 Discussion of applications for the three-lens system

314 4.1 Adaptive laser beam shaping

315 The presented three-lens system has been successfully applied in nonlinear optics, such as
316 stimulated Brillouin scattering and stimulated Raman scattering¹⁰, where independent tuning of
317 nonlinear interaction length and beam shape is beneficial. The device and method of tuning is in
318 contrast with zoom-based approaches combined with a fixed-focus lens¹¹, which adjust
319 magnification but lack independent control over focus position. As the three-lens system avoids
320 an internal focus position, it is also well-suited for other high-energy laser applications, including
321 materials processing or plasma generation.

322 4.2 Tunable imaging

323 The parallel mode and the direct imaging mode from Sec. 2.5 enable applications in which the
324 output rays from L_1 are parallel or form a direct image. The parallel mode might be suitable for
325 detectors with on-board integrated imaging optics, i.e. smartphones, the eye or even professional
326 cameras. It may also be possible to use the three-lens system or its principle as a distinct building
327 block. If the form factor is allowed to be large enough, the three-lens system is expected to support
328 applications ranging from microscopic and close-up macroscopic imaging to long-range terrestrial
329 and astronomical viewing. With more feasible form factors, of course, these applications need to
330 be split into at least two groups, each with optimized lens configurations (see Sec. 4.3).

331 In direct imaging mode, the three-lens system already shows properties of a varifocal objective,
332 but control over image position has not been established yet (see Secs. 2.5 and 5.2). Table 1
333 summarizes some objective properties of the special case of configuration (b) from Fig. 3 using a
334 variable iris (1 – 40 mm) on L_3 and a $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ detector with one megapixel in the image plane.

335 **Table 1** Some objective properties of the special case with $l_2 = f_2 = 20 \text{ cm}$ and $3.7 \text{ cm} \leq l_1 \leq 20 \text{ cm}$, showing the
336 f-number (f/#), field of view (FOV) and hyperfocal depth of field (DOF) for different focal lengths and apertures.

$f_{\text{sys,SL}}$	f/# (min – max)	FOV	DOF (max – min)
55 mm	f/1.4 – f/55	5.2°	11 – 440 m
150 mm	f/3.8 – f/150	1.9°	30 – 1200 m
500 mm	f/12.5 – f/500	0.6°	100 – 4000 m

337 4.3 Combination with different actuators

338 The steepness of the functional dependence of f_{sys} and M in the parallel mode, as shown in Fig. 3,
 339 can be either beneficial or detrimental, depending on the actuator system and the available or
 340 desired form factor. To quantify the achievable resolution in setting f_{sys} , the special case scenario
 341 from Sec. 2.3, with two different lens triplets, is used. It is assumed, that distance $l_2 = f_2$ is set
 342 with a precision of $\Delta l_2 = 10 \mu\text{m}$. For the tuning of l_1 , we consider a 10 cm setscrew with sub-
 343 millimeter coarse positioning, carrying a voice coil motor (VCM) that provides a 1 mm fine-tuning
 344 range with a resolution of $\Delta l_1 = 1 \mu\text{m}$. Lens L_1 is mounted directly on the VCM. To find suitable
 345 focal lengths for the triplets, Eqns. (10), (12), (14) and (15) were reverse-mapped onto
 346 (f_1, f_2, f_3, l_1) with $f_{\text{sys}} > 2000 \text{ cm}$ and $l_1 + f_2 = 40 \text{ cm}$ for a far-field configuration and $f_{\text{sys}} >$
 347 50 cm and $l_1 + f_2 = 8 \text{ cm}$ for a more compact near-field configuration. For both configurations
 348 $M = 4$ and $\Delta f_{\text{sys}} < 1 \text{ cm}$ were used. Subsequently, an extra propagation distance for l_1 was added
 349 to accommodate lower values of f_{sys} . This gives the final form factor l_{total} . Table 2 summarizes
 350 the results for different values of f_{sys} .

351 **Table 2** Special case configurations for parallel near- and far-field imaging, each with $M = 4$. All units in cm.

Application	$f_1 / f_2 / f_3$	l_{total}	Range f_{sys}	$f_{\text{sys}} \pm \Delta f_{\text{sys}}$	l_1
Near-field	-1.2/ 4.8/ 45	≈ 10	$10 - \infty$	50 ± 0.011	3.55
				500 ± 1.19	3.13
				2000 ± 19.25	3.10
Far-field	-6/ 24/ 250	≈ 45	$100 - \infty$	500 ± 0.04	16.85
				2000 ± 0.74	15.98
				20000 ± 75.7	15.72

352 Upon inspecting Fig. 3, it is evident why the mapping favoured large values of f_3 , as these shift
 353 the pole towards the Galilean pole at $f_{\text{sys}} = f_3$, which is a totally horizontal isoline. As a result,
 354 the pole line becomes more horizontal itself, comparable to the $f_{\text{sys}} = 100 \text{ cm}$ isoline from graph
 355 (a). This reduces the sensitivity to errors in l_2 in Eq. (14).

356 However, if we would now allow l_2 to vary across those nearly horizontal isolines, as in the general
 357 case of the three-lens system, even a large change in l_2 will cause only a minor shift in f_{sys} . If this
 358 extra tuning range is large enough to contain the initial error made by setting f_{sys} with l_1 , the
 359 system effectively realizes an optical coarse/fine adjustment mechanism, analogous to the

360 setscrew/VCM combination. In this way, the three-lens system imposes a fine-tuning mask on the
361 generalized Galilean telescope, albeit now M changes depending on where the f_{sys} isoline
362 intersects the $M(l_1, l_2)$ surface. Strategies to mitigate this coupling will be outlined in Sec. 5.2.

363

364 **5 Conclusion**

365 *5.1 Summary and interpretation*

366 The three-lens system and the matrix-analytical treatment introduced in this work enable
367 independent control of focus position and magnification over a wide range. Herein, lens L_3 in
368 conjunction with distance l_2 can be viewed as a multiplier of Galilean beam properties which,
369 itself are controlled by l_1 . The intermediate lens L_2 plays a central role in shaping both the width
370 and location of the near field high-magnification range region, which becomes maximally tunable
371 at decent form factors when the lens distances satisfy $f_{\text{sys}} \approx f_2$. Additionally, in the special case,
372 L_2 determines distance l_2 and scales the change of f_{sys} with respect to a change in l_1 . A
373 fundamental limit of the magnification range occurs when the focus position coincides with the
374 third lens ($f_{\text{sys}} = f_3$), where the beam arrives collimated at L_3 and the functionality of the three-
375 lens system collapses into a Galilean telescope with an additional lens.

376 In contrast to many traditional optical systems, which are often constructed from predefined lens
377 blocks and analyzed primarily via raytracing techniques or equivalent focal length models, the
378 approach in this work relies on an explicit analytical treatment of the paraxial matrix elements.
379 The system is explored through its internal configuration space, parameterized directly by lens
380 distances l_i and focal lengths f_i , and linked to optical observables such as system focus position
381 and magnification. Herein, the number of independently tunable mechanical variables must match
382 the number of optical variables.

383 Thus, it is not only the optical system itself that is important, but also the method of analysis: the
384 analytical path can open the door to a deeper understanding of optical tunability and may inspire
385 future hybrid design strategies that combine analytical treatment of matrix-derived equations with
386 numerical optimization.

387 5.2 Outlook

388 An alternative geometry arises when the third lens is placed before the Galilean pair, effectively
389 relocating the tunability region into the object space. Preliminary experiments¹⁰ show that this
390 configuration produces a nearly symmetric magnification curve centered around $M = 1$, and
391 unlike the standard three-lens system, it does not exhibit a collapsing node or a tunable collimated
392 state. A more systematic theoretical and numerical analysis of the object-space configuration is
393 currently under development, following a similar approach as presented here.

394 Future work may also extend the present paraxial matrix approach to include thick-lens elements
395 and their wavelength-dependent focal lengths. Additionally, using a Gaussian beam description
396 with q -parameter propagation may reveal how the tunability affects beam waist and divergence.

397 The analytical separation of focus and magnification by the three-lens system makes it attractive
398 to explore extensions with a fourth lens. A fourth element could allow the system to operate with
399 divergent or convergent input beams while preserving tunability. This can be beneficial for direct
400 imaging with fixed detectors. Alternatively, a fourth lens may enable chromatic correction. For
401 example the theoretical conditions, Eqns. (2) and (3) presented within this work could extend to
402 $A_{\text{red}}(l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4 = f_{\text{sys,red}}) = 0$, $A_{\text{blue}}(l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4 = f_{\text{sys,blue}}) = 0$, $A(l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4 = 0) = M$,
403 resulting in three mechanical degrees of freedom and allowing linear decoupling of wavelength
404 dependent focusing.

405 Another promising future direction involves adding a two-element tuning layer to the three-lens
406 system, using two additional optical elements with very large focal lengths, i.e. stressed plane-
407 parallel glass plates. Together with two distances, between them and the three-lens system, these
408 form a new three-lens system with four mechanical degrees of freedom. The original three-lens
409 system (L'_3) then defines the dynamic range of possible values (f_{sys}, M), whereas the new three-
410 lens system defines a new (l'_1, l'_2) subspace at every point of the original (l_1, l_2) space, thereby
411 defining the resolution ($\Delta f_{\text{sys}}, \Delta M$). This approach is similar in spirit to the combined coarse/fine
412 drive system described in Sec. 4.3, but now with full matrix-optical control and, in theory, close
413 to ideal precision.

414

415 *Disclosures*

416 The author is also the main inventor in patent publication US 2020/0388977 A1, which covers an
417 earlier version of the three-lens configuration. The present work develops a new theoretical
418 framework and analysis that significantly expands upon the original concept. The patent is no
419 longer maintained.

420 *Code and Data Availability*

421 Python codes from numerical simulations or derivations of equations from the theoretical
422 description can be provided upon reasonable request by the author (see email address).

423 *Acknowledgments*

424 ChatGPT-4 helped in building the Python codes for the plots on Sec. 3 under full supervision and
425 validation by the author.

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 453 applications such as molecular probes or temporal laser beam manipulation.

454

455 **Caption List**

456

457 **Fig. 1** Schematic of the three-lens system and a laser beam allowing independent tuning of focus
 458 position and magnification. Lenses L_1 , L_2 and L_3 are separated by independently adjustable
 459 distances l_1 and l_2 . Variables f_i denote focal lengths, l_3 is the propagation distance after L_3 , Δy_{in}
 460 and Δy_{out} are input and output laser beam diameters, $\alpha_{in,l}$ and $\alpha_{out,l}$ denote the input and output
 461 divergence of the laser beam, respectively.

462 **Fig. 2** Accessible magnification range (gray area) with envelope M_{max} and M_{min} (black solid
 463 lines) for each focus position. $f_1 = -5$ cm, $f_2 = 20$ cm and $f_3 = 50$ cm (a), 40 cm (b), 30 cm
 464 (c), 20 cm (d). The magnification of the general Galilean telescope M^{Gal} is shown for
 465 comparison (black dashed line).

466 **Fig. 3** Precision of tunability Δf_{sys} with $f_3 = 50$ cm (a), 30 cm (b) and 20 cm (c), and ΔM (d).
 467 All graphs have $f_1 = 5$ cm and $f_2 = 20$ cm. Isolines for f_{sys} and M are shown as white solid lines.
 468 Areas with $f_{sys} < 0$ or $M < 0$ are shown as white surface.

469 **Table 1** Some objective properties of the special case with $l_2 = f_2 = 20$ cm and 3.7 cm $\leq l_1 \leq$
 470 20 cm, showing the f-number (f/#), field of view (FOV) and hyperfocal depth of field (DOF) for
 471 different focal lengths and apertures.

472 **Table 2** Special case configurations for parallel near- and far-field imaging, each with $M = 4$. All
 473 units in cm.